

PROTECTION OF LABOUR RIGHTS OF MINORS: PROBLEMS OF THEORY AND PRACTICE

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Abstract: Despite the regulation of labor rights of minors at the legislative level, in practice we continue to face problems and contradictions arising in the implementation of the right to work by minors. In this article we have identified and identified the most significant problems faced by the subjects of law in the implementation of labor activity. In this article, the ways of solving these problems are proposed.

Key words: minors, labour rights, age, protection of rights, employment contract.

Аннотация: Несмотря на урегулирование трудовых прав несовершеннолетних на законодательном уровне, на практике мы продолжаем сталкиваться с проблемами и противоречиями, возникающими при реализации права на труд несовершеннолетними. В настоящей статье мы выделили и определили наиболее значимые проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются рассматриваемые субъекты права при осуществлении трудовой деятельности. В настоящей статье предложены пути решения обозначенных проблем.

Ключевые слова: несовершеннолетние, трудовые права, возраст, защита прав, трудовой договор.

Annotatsiya: Voyaga yetmaganlarning mehnat huquqlari qonunchilik darajasida hal qilinishiga qaramay, amalda biz voyaga yetmaganlarning mehnat huquqini amalga oshirishda yuzaga keladigan muammolar va qarama-qarshiliklarga duch kelishda davom etamiz. Ushbu maqolada biz ko'rib chiqilayotgan huquq sub'ektlari mehnat faoliyatini amalga oshirishda duch keladigan eng muhim muammolar aniqlanib, ko'rib chiqilgan. Ushbu maqolada ko'rsatilgan muammolarni hal qilish usullari taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: voyaga yetmaganlar, mehnat huquqlari, yoshi, huquqlarni himoya qilish, mehnat shartnomasi.

For many minors, work is an opportunity for self-affirmation, an opportunity to feel the first independence, to acquire pocket money for their own expenses. A lot of schoolchildren are enthusiastically looking for an opportunity to earn their own money during the holidays. Who knows, the number of minors who are engaged in films and television is now increasing, and they are engaged in other types of creative activities. Despite the ongoing process of decentralization of labor law for more than a quarter of a century, it is obvious that the main responsibility to protect The labor rights of minors are borne by the State. This does not contradict international legal standards of labor rights, since their observance and protection is the duty of the State. Our country has ratified the conventions of the International Labour Organization, which directly regulate the working conditions of children and adolescents, as well as two ILO conventions prohibiting forced labor. At the same time, the problem of juvenile labor in our country is often ignored, misjudged and, as a result, not solved.

State policy is aimed at protecting children and combating the exploitation of child labor, yes, since a minor is a subject of law who needs special protection. That is why domestic legislation pays close attention to the protection of the labor rights of minors.

1. One of the important problems that one has to face is the implementation of work duties by a minor without concluding an employment contract. Due to the requirements provided for by law, employers simply do not want to enter into an employment contract with minors, thereby burdening themselves with additional responsibilities and expenses.

We see the solution to this problem in the following:

1. Establishment of job quotas for minors. The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not contain provisions on granting minors a quota for employment. This prerogative applies to local government authorities. In order to provide minors with jobs by providing quotas, it is necessary either to make appropriate changes to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Employment of the population".

2. The establishment of preferential tax regimes for employers to encourage The latter are used to attract children to engage in legitimate work;

3. Creation of special labor groups for children at the municipal level, whose activities will be aimed at attracting minors to socially useful work during the holidays. Schoolchildren work in these groups under an employment contract, who also benefit the city, because they carry out landscaping of streets, minor repairs of playgrounds and so on.

2. The next problem is the representation of a minor when changing an employment contract. The labor legislation prescribes whose consent must be obtained at the conclusion (of one of the parents and the guardianship authority of Article 118 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan), termination of the employment contract (Article 269 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation), however, when making changes to the terms of the employment contract, nothing is said in the legislation, which means that in this case general provisions provided for in the revised Article 72 of the Labor Code of the Russian Federation. In our opinion, to ensure the protection of the labor rights of minors In order to prevent them from making obviously unfavorable conditions in the employment contract, it is necessary to involve the legal representative of the minor and the guardianship and guardianship authority.

3. By virtue of Article 414 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "Persons under the age of eighteen are employed only after a preliminary mandatory medical examination and in the future, until they reach the age of eighteen, they are subject to mandatory medical examination annually." These medical examinations are carried out at the expense of the employer. The Order of the Minister of Health dated 07/10/2012 No. 200 draws attention to this obligation. However, to date, in judicial practice there are cases when the employer, ignoring this obligation, employs a minor without a mandatory preliminary medical examination. As a result, he is subject to administrative punishment for violating labor laws.

4. Labor legislation provides for a direct ban on the employment of minors at night, weekends and non-working holidays. In one of the cases considered by the city court, the head of the legal entity, the employer, engaged underage workers to work on weekends, violating the requirements established by Article 417 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since these persons were not creative workers of the media,

cinematography organizations, television and video shooting groups, theaters, theater and concert halls organizations, circuses, as well as persons involved in the creation and (or) performance (exhibiting) of works.

In the present case, the employer referred to the fact that the suspension of work was due to – technical and organizational conditions are impossible, and two days off that do not coincide with the general days off were provided to employees on a rolling schedule, in accordance with this, they cannot be brought to administrative responsibility. Thus, the employer, referring to Article 207 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, believed that there was no element of an administrative offense in his actions. Meanwhile, the court pointed out that the norm of Article 417 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan is special in relation to Article 207 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Russian Federation, and therefore the latter is not applicable in this case. Moreover, during the trial, it was established that the employer also employed adult employees, whom it is not prohibited by labor legislation to involve in work on weekends.

Due to the fact that currently more and more minors want to work, in our opinion it is necessary to increase legal literacy among the population in the field of labor relations, which will entail solving the problems disclosed in this article. To implement this proposal, we see holding special open lectures and seminars aimed at studying the basic provisions of labor law in order to further prevent violations of labor rights. Such education should be carried out not only among young people, but also to involve all citizens, as often parents, due to their illiteracy, cannot protect your child from the illegal actions of the employer.

Summarizing the above, it should be said that in our state, the work of minors is legally regulated. The main problems arise from the fact that the employment relationship is not They are recorded properly, and the population of the country does not have knowledge of the basics of labor law, which negatively affects labor relations, entailing violations of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens in general, and minors in particular.

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